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Deliverable D7.5 - *First update of the strategy for Addressing the Ethics and Intellectual Property Rights in the Project*

WP7 – *Project coordination and management*

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HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-02-01- Blueprint demonstration for
co-created effective, efficient and resilient networks of MPAs

Document History

Deliverable Title	First update of the strategy for Addressing the Ethics and Intellectual Property Rights in the Project
Brief Description	This deliverable provides an update to the first strategy for addressing the ethics and Intellectual Property Rights in Blue4All. It aims to identify the key ethical and legal requirements of the BLUE4ALL project in relation to the involvement of research contributors (i.e. stakeholders) for workshops, surveys and interviews, and particularly the identification and recruitment thereof. It also identifies the main Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues to consider in BLUE4ALL to ensure compliance with the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement. These are identified as copyright and database protection, including confidential information, while following the EC's "Open Science, Open Innovation, Open to the World" agenda and applying the FAIR principles to all project outputs. The project's authorship policy is also outlined.
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14/12/2023	2.0	Lawrence Whatley (VLIZ), Lennert Schepers (VLIZ)	D7.5: Added an explanation of the ethical issues encountered when carrying out activities in non-EU countries (section 6.6) and Blue4All's authorship policy (section 8). Minor edits made to sections 2 (Introduction), 3 (Ethical Principles under Horizon Europe), and 4 (Intellectual Property Rights under Horizon Europe), and annex 10.1 (Informed Consent Form).
20/12/2023	2.1	Lawrence Whatley (VLIZ), Lennert Schepers (VLIZ), Bob Rumes (RBINS), Ivana Stojanovic (Submariner), Steven Degraer (RBINS)	D7.5: Deliverable edited based on comments received from reviewers.

Abbreviations

CC	Creative Commons
DMP	Data Management Plan
D	Deliverable
DESCA	Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement
EBSA	Ecologically or Biologically Significant Marine Area
EB	Ethics Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EP	Exploitation Plan
FAIR	Findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HEU	Horizon Europe
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
LP	Lead Partner
MPA	Marine protected area
OS	Open Science
SEG	Stakeholder Engagement Group
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable focuses on the ethical and legal requirements of the BLUE4ALL project in relation to:

1. Research contributors (i.e. stakeholders) for workshops, surveys and interviews, and particularly the identification and recruitment thereof. The practices and criteria used to identify, and recruit research participants are clearly formulated. Specifically, more detailed practical implementation methods and frameworks are further elaborated upon within D4.1 (Information sites engagement plan) and D6.1 (Dissemination and communication plan). In addition to that, research participants will be provided with informed consent procedures, including an informed consent template for research participation in the Stakeholder Engagement Groups established for each of the 13 Living Labs (D4.3). Matters of data processing are also handled in relation to data management of research participants with further information on GDPR compliance, available within D7.3 (Data Management Plan).

2. The main Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues to consider in BLUE4ALL to ensure compliance with the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement. These are identified as copyright and database protection, including confidential information, while following the EC's "Open Science, Open Innovation, Open to the World" agenda and applying the FAIR principles to all project outputs. Further information on processes ensuring IPR compliance and adherence to Open Science principles is available in D7.3 (DMP).

This deliverable provides an update to D7.1 (Strategy for Addressing the Ethics and Intellectual Property Rights in the Project). Additions to D7.1 are highlighted in italics; the most significant additions are an explanation of the ethical issues encountered when carrying out activities in non-EU countries (section 6.6) and BLUE4ALL's authorship policy (section 8). Minor edits were also made to sections 2 (Introduction), 3 (Ethical Principles under Horizon Europe) and 4 (Intellectual Property Rights under Horizon Europe), and annex 10.1 (Informed Consent Form). This deliverable will be updated in month 24 as D7.6 (Second update of the strategy for Addressing the Ethics and Intellectual Property Rights in the Project).

2. Introduction

This report clarifies the roles and procedures for addressing the ethics and Intellectual Property Rights in the project BLUE4ALL to ensure consistent application of legal and ethical frameworks, and assist the full partnership in the appropriate implementation of activities and the monitoring of ethics aspects and IPR protection. *This deliverable is the first update of the original Strategy for Addressing the Ethics and Intellectual Property Rights in the Project (D7.1) and will be further updated in month 24 as D7.6.*

Utilising the ethical self-assessment in accordance with European Horizon Europe guidelines, *the following ethical issues were identified for the BLUE4ALL project: humans used in research for non-medical studies, the collection and processing of personal data, and activities carried out in non-EU countries.* The key data to be collected from stakeholders studied in BLUE4ALL will be reviewed by the dedicated Ethics Board.

This document also addresses BLUE4ALL's general approach to managing IPR. BLUE4ALL will follow the EC's "Open Science, Open Innovation, Open to the World" agenda and apply the FAIR principles to all project outputs. As stated in the DG Research & Innovation's study on Open Science (OS) and Intellectual Property Rights (2022), the OS paradigm poses new challenges to IPR. Here, we address the issue in a general manner, while the deliverables D7.3 (Data Management Plan) and D6.1 (Dissemination and Communication Plan) address the concrete IPR issues to be considered when applying the OS agenda in relation to data management and exploitation and dissemination of results.

3. Ethical principles under Horizon Europe

Ethics is an integral part of research projects, which is also underlined by the European Commission (EC), specifically under Horizon Europe (HEU) research projects. The core of the ethical dilemma in research projects is to find a balance between two (or more) contradicting values. Though there are a number of absolute rules and regulations, the big challenge of ethics is one of judgement. The BLUE4ALL project will follow ethical compliance to respect the legal framework but also to enhance the quality of the research. We will follow existing EU, international and national guidelines. The HEU ethical requirements are anchored in the regulation HE Framework Programme Regulation 2021/695: Eligible actions and ethical principles (Article 18) and Ethics (Article 19). In Article 19 (1) of the regulation it is stated that:

"Actions carried out under the Programme shall comply with ethical principles and relevant Union, national and international law, including the Charter and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its Supplementary Protocols."

We follow therefore the ethical principles that are stated in this article and how they are applicable in the context of humans used in research, namely the principle of proportionality, the right to privacy, the right to protection of personal data, the right to physical and mental integrity of a person, the right to non-discrimination, and the need to ensure high levels of human health protection.

Some activities will be carried out in non-EU countries, e.g., in the Information Sites located in Montenegro, Albania, and Brazil, and the Living Lab located in Montenegro. BLUE4ALL will therefore ensure that all activities in these countries would be allowed in a Member State in accordance with Article 19 of the [HEU Regulation 2021/695](#), which lays out the ethical principles that all actions carried out under HEU must adhere to.

Personal data might be collected when engaging with stakeholders through interviews, surveys, workshops, or online applications. *Data protection measures related to the collection and management of personal data are outlined in section 6.4 and D7.3 (Data Management Plan).*

4. Intellectual Property Rights under Horizon Europe

IPR under Horizon Europe are set out in the Grant Agreement art. 16 and Annex 5 (Specific Rules). *They are further elaborated in the Data Management Plan (D7.3) and the Consortium Agreement, e.g. as based on the DESCAs template. The grant and consortium agreements define the ownership of and access rights to results, as well as the rules governing joint ownership, exploitation and dissemination of results, confidentiality, access rights to existing background, and Open Science.*

Based on the DG Research and Innovation's report study on Open Science and Intellectual Property Rights (2022), considerations should always be made regarding how to balance OS and IPR:

- The concrete application of IPR and OS principles in relation to exploitation and dissemination of results, i.e. this should be included in the exploitation plan (D6.4).
- The concrete application of IPR in relation to the FAIR principles (findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability of data) i.e. this should be included in the data management plan (D7.3) and there should be a defined process for checking the validity of the consent of the rights holder or whether an exception/limitation applies.

5. Role of the Ethics Board in BLUE4ALL

The project has established the Ethics Board (EB) involving all WP leads and some of the Advisory Board participants to warrant compliance with fundamental ethical principles present in the Nuremberg Code, European Textbook on Ethics in Research, and EC Ethics Appraisal Procedure. The EB will ensure consistent application of the legal and ethical frameworks referenced in this document, and will assist the full partnership in the appropriate implementation of activities and the monitoring of ethics aspects including the 'do no significant harm' principle and IPR protection. The EB will specifically review documents, tasks and deliverables mentioned in this strategy. Generally, the EB will be involved by the LP (RBINS) as soon as any ethical or IPR related question arises beyond the issues already identified. *During the first meeting of the EB, planned for month 13 (January 2024), the project's authorship policy (section 8) will be discussed and modified.*

6. Implementing HEU ethical principles in BLUE4ALL

During the BLUE4ALL project, surveys, workshops and interviews with several stakeholders will be conducted. Participation thereof will be entirely voluntary. An informed consent procedure will be used to inform participants of the voluntary nature of their involvement, project aims, use of data, and data protection regulation and implications of the research participation. This chapter describes the procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants

with reference to the relevant HEU ethical principles, the informed consent procedure and the data and sampling collection of research participants. *These principles will apply to all activities carried out under BLUE4ALL, whether in an EU Member State or a non-EU country.*

6.1 Ethical principles in context

Ethical principles under Horizon Europe can be applied to the context of research participation:

- The principle of proportionality, meaning that cause and effect or action and consequences should be proportional. Questions posed during interviews and surveys should be proportional to the project aims;
- The right to privacy, meaning the absence of public attention. Information collected during interviews and surveys will be treated confidentially.
- The right to protection of personal data. Resulting data from interviews, surveys and workshops will be protected and stored securely in compliance with latest GDPR 2016/697 regulations, which are further specified in D7.3 (DMP)
- The right to physical and mental integrity of a person. No physical or mental pressure will be applied in any form during the recruitment procedure and the informed consent procedure
- The right to non-discrimination. No discrimination during the identification and recruitment of research participants will take place. Meaning, no discrimination based on colour, race, gender, religion, political preference, age, nationality or marital status. The BLUE4ALL consortium has an international character with partners with a headquarters in over 13 different countries and people from many nationalities are represented within the consortium
- The need to ensure high levels of human health protection. We ensure that research participants will only participate in interviews, surveys and workshops under high levels of human health protection.

The above principals will be adhered to throughout the BLUE4ALL project and applied in the communication and dissemination activities, recruitment and building of Information sites, Stakeholder Engagement Groups in Living Labs, as well as the identification, recruitment, data gathering, and processing of survey and workshop participants. They will in particular be addressed in the specific contexts of WP4 (D4.1, D4.3), WP5 (D5.1), and WP6 (Tasks 6.3 and 6.4).

Furthermore, guidelines on safety and protection in relation to the activities to be carried out in the context of the project (not related to testing or administration of human based research, as this is not applicable in this context) will be adhered to, providing robust ethical standards to those working within the project.

6.2 Identification and recruitment of research participants

The identification and recruitment of research participants for interviews, surveys and workshops is further elaborated upon within the efforts of WP4: Deliverable 4.1 (Information sites

engagement plan), and Deliverable 4.2 (Living Lab testing package) and Deliverable 4.3 (Stakeholder Engagement Groups in Living labs).

In general, participants are recruited from existing networks and approached during conferences and workshops. Such networks include the existing scientific, professional, and industrial connections, working groups, and initiatives for which BLUE4ALL partners and the consortium as a whole is involved with. Requests for research participants may also be communicated through the project website and the project newsletter to engage with and utilise the community interested in the developments of the project. Furthermore, additional recruitment procedure may be developed in order to fulfil gaps existing in the already accessible pool of candidates, these can include directed queries to governance and research networks cited as of high relevance, advice on networks and participants from the Information sites and Stakeholder Engagement Groups in Living Labs from task deliverables 4.1 and 4.3 respectively.

When identifying and recruiting research participants (i.e. stakeholders), all partners of the BLUE4ALL project will comply with the ethical principles. Stakeholders will be identified and grouped in a stakeholder register that is internal to the BLUE4ALL project. The register allows to visualise e.g. relative power and interest of stakeholders on a relative scale, however, this will not be done on a specific user by user basis but rather the power structure of generalised groupings of potential and identified stakeholder groups, thereby not utilising personalised data from any of the research participants and nullifying any concerns towards personal information protection as this will not be applicable. *As stated in D4.2, all members of Stakeholder Engagement Groups (SEGs) will sign a Letter of Intent, thereby agreeing to be involved in the BLUE4ALL project and to contribute to the project's objectives. If necessary, for instance if their personal data will be collected, SEG members will also sign the Informed Consent Form (Annex 10.1).*

6.3 Data collection and data protection

This paragraph describes the GDPR directive, its principles and how the BLUE4ALL project adopts protection measures to assure fair adequate and informed research participation.

For data collection during interviews, surveys and workshops, we comply to the latest GDPR regulation (GDPR 2016/697). In Article 4(1) it is stated that personal data means

“any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.”

In Article 4(2) it is stated that processing means

“any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection,

recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction.”

According to the EC’s guidance on ethics and data protection (2021), data protection should be included by design and default in the context of research and development by applying the following measures when relevant:

- Pseudonymisation and anonymisation of personal data;
- data minimisation;
- applied cryptography (e.g. encryption and hashing);
- using data-protection focused service providers and storage platforms; and
- arrangements that enable data subjects to exercise their fundamental rights (e.g. as regards direct access to their personal data and consent to its use or transfer).

6.3.1 Personal Data

Personal data collected for the purposes of the BLUE4ALL project, will only be stored, analysed and used anonymously. Personal data will not be made public and will have restrictions for usage (i.e., only within the project and for the purposes of the defined tasks).

This document focuses on the processes related to involvement of stakeholders in research. Further specification of the GDPR compliance in relation to all storage and processing of personal data is covered by *D7.3 (Data Management Plan)*, which will be updated throughout the project.

6.4 Data protection measures

The above considerations can be translated to data protection measures. These will be followed and applied where possible.

6.4.1 Data collection

Data resulting from surveys, workshops and interviews will be collected according to the minimisation principle. This means that we only collect data that is adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the project aims. Thus, the only information collected via interviews, meetings/workshops related to the information sites & stakeholder engagement groups in WP4. An informed consent statement should inform all research participants of the terms and conditions. Interactive webinars will also be sources of information collection serving general knowledge exchange between the MPA managers, planners, industry and researchers. Information may be collected in an audio-visual format (e.g. video of the webinar) and explicit agreement will be required from each participant for the recording and publishing of the material.

6.4.2 Anonymisation and pseudonymisation

Any data will be anonymised, where possible, and else data will be pseudonymised. The Data Protection Working Party, which is an independent European advisory body on data protection and privacy, published a document on Anonymisation techniques (Opinion 05/2014 on

Anonymisation Techniques, 2014). Here generalisation, randomisation techniques are discussed. Also, pseudonymisation, which is different from anonymisation is considered here. For anonymisation, the data must be stripped until the point where the data subject is no longer identifiable. Anonymisation techniques like aggregation will be applied if relevant. Here data is displayed only in total scores, omitting individual responses. For example, age 25 will be grouped in the category age 20-30. If anonymisation is not achievable, pseudonymisation techniques can be applied, so that the source of information cannot be traced back to the data. Direct identifiers (e.g. names) will be replaced with indirect identifiers (e.g. numbers). Data masking could be applied, where some personal identifiers are stripped out, while others remain.

6.4.3 Data Security, storage and encryption

Practical data security, storage and encryption measures provided by the European University Institute (EUI, 2019) that will be used where possible:

- User authentication: verify user by a password, considering length, a mix of letters and no ties to your personal information;
- Access control: a mechanism to allow or deny access to certain data;
- Storage security: storing data in a way that prevent unauthorised access, for example by operating system controls, use of passwords to access electronic files, local encrypted storage, database encryption;
- Data retention will cover the duration of the project and not longer;
- Communication security: safe electronic communication for transferring data: encrypted communications (SSL/TLS, safe URLs starting with https://); firewall systems and access control lists; anti-virus and anti-malware systems; protect data when physically transferred.

6.4.4 Data Transfer

Regarding the data collected for the purposes of the communication and dissemination activities of the project, they will not be transferred to third parties either in the original form or in copies. Data might be published in reports, scientific publications, and other forms of publication, however, in anonymised form only.

The EB, including legal experts at various partner institutes, will guarantee that this process, including the information for the individuals about data protection issues, fully complies with national and EU laws.

6.4.5 Informed consent procedure

Individuals participating in any form of stakeholder engagement activities that involve the collection of data, will be informed comprehensively about the intended use of the information collected from them and have to agree to the data collection for scientific purposes with their active approval in form of a written consent. In addition, individuals will be informed about data

security, anonymity and use of data as well as asked for accordance. The Informed consent form template is attached in Annex 10.1 of this document.

6.5 Website data collection

The BLUE4ALL website should serve as a source of information on the project. The following personal data might be stored while using the website: name of internet domain, IP address of the accessing computer, pages visited and actions performed throughout the website.

The data may be processed in order to optimize the website by improving the quality of the available information, website ergonomics, website management, website navigation and to generate statistics from this information. The collected data will not be provided to any third party or processed in a manner inconsistent with the purposes for which they have been initially collected, without prejudice to any applicable legal provision of any kind, particularly in the matter of data retention, as will also be specified in Deliverable 7.3 (DMP).

The website is anticipated to store cookies. These are small text files that are saved on the computer, which the browser can access. They increase the user-friendliness of the website. In case the website uses cookies, a pop-up will ask you for a permission first.

6.6 Activities in non-EU countries

BLUE4ALL will conduct certain activities in the following non-EU countries, none of which are low or lower-middle income countries:

- *Montenegro (Platamuni, Katič, and Stari Ulcinj Living Lab; part of the South Adriatic Ionian Strait EBSA Information Site)*
- *Albania (part of the South Adriatic Ionian Strait EBSA Information Site)*
- *Brazil (Parque Nacional Marinho de Fernando de Noronha Information Site)*

Since BLUE4ALL is an EU-funded project, the EU's ethics requirements, outlined in section 6.1, apply to all project activities irrespective of where they take place. The activities carried out in the three non-EU countries identified above are not foreseen to raise any ethical issues in addition to those already identified (humans used in research for non-medical studies, the collection and processing of personal data). No local resources from these countries will be used, and no non-data materials will be transported from the EU to these countries or vice-versa. Furthermore, there are no specific safety measures which are required to carry out any Blue4All-related activities in these countries. Future activities may also take place in other non-EU countries; in this case the same ethical requirements described in this section and 6.1 will apply and any ethical issues raised by this will be addressed by the EB and explained in D7.6.

Personal data may be collected during the project's activities in these non-EU countries, namely interviews, surveys and workshops carried out by WP4. If this is the case, all data collection and protection procedures must be in accordance with (1.) the laws of the country in which the data was collected, and (2.) EU law. The GDPR applies to all data-processing procedures carried out by Blue4All, both within and outside of the EU. Any partner(s) who collect and/or process data in non-

EU countries should determine what legal obligations apply based on local and EU laws and take whatever action is necessary to comply with them. Partners must also be able to demonstrate compliance upon request.

When personal data collected from non-EU countries is exported to the EU, research participants must understand and provide their consent by signing the Informed Consent Form (Annex 10.1). In this case, the data protection measures outlined in section 6.4 will be implemented, including pseudonymisation and anonymisation where appropriate. To ensure that personal data are transferred securely, the appropriate organisational and technical measures described in sections 6.4.3 and 6.4.4 should be taken.

7. Implementing IPR in BLUE4ALL

To ensure that all knowledge and intellectual property generated by BLUE4ALL is managed correctly and adequately protected, the BLUE4ALL Consortium Agreement addresses the ownership and management of both project results and pre-existing rights (i.e., background included), as well as access rights and confidential information. Results are owned by the partner that generates them, including the case of joint ownership and the principles governing this.

The main IPR issues to consider in BLUE4ALL are copyright and database protection in relation to datasets and publications, while following the EC's "Open Science, Open Innovation, Open to the World" agenda and applying the FAIR principles to all project outputs. As stated in the DG Research & Innovation's study on Open Science (OS) and Intellectual Property Rights (2022), the OS paradigm poses new challenges to IPR, but the two are in no way incompatible.

In BLUE4ALL, the knowledge co-elaboration and open science approach is reflected in several inclusive practices and co-creation methods applied (e.g. T4.2, T4.3 and WP5: the development of an online blueprint). The BLUE4ALL research will be made openly available unless otherwise explicitly specified, and under the conditions that no confidential information is involved and that appropriate identification of origin and conditions of reuse is applied (e.g. CC licenses).

The BLUE4ALL project will follow the FAIR principles:

- *Findable*: The data and metadata can be found by the community after their publication, using search tools.
- *Accessible*: (Meta)data are accessible and can therefore be downloaded by other researchers using their identifiers.
- *Interoperable*: Both the data and the metadata should be described following the rules of the community, using open standards, in order to allow for their exchange and reuse.
- *Reusable*: (Meta)data can be reused by other researchers, since their origin and conditions of reuse are clear.

D6.1 further addresses the dissemination and communication strategy.

D6.4 will further address the means of exploitation applied in the project

D7.3 (DMP) will further address the protection of IPR in relation to the findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability of data produced under BLUE4ALL.

8. Authorship Policy for Scientific Publications

An appropriate authorship policy for scientific publications produced in BLUE4ALL will ensure that authors (1.) receive the academic credit they deserve and (2.) are responsible and accountable for the published work. This policy may differ from the authorship policy for deliverables. Partners involved in a task or research activity should start discussing the authorship of the scientific publication(s) as early and openly as possible before writing the publication and continue this discussion throughout the timeframe of the work. The authorship policy was partly adapted from the [criteria](#) developed by the Internal Committee of Medical Journal Editors and will be discussed during the next General Assembly (month 13, January 2024). Any changes to the policy will be included in the Second update of the strategy for Addressing the Ethics and Intellectual Property Rights in the Project (D7.6) in month 24.

8.1 Authorship Threshold Criteria

Partners must meet all four of the following criteria to be considered authors of scientific publications, and must therefore be identified as authors in the publication:

- 1. Substantial contributions to at least three of the following tasks:
 - a. The conception or design of the publication*
 - b. The acquisition of data*
 - c. Data analysis and interpretation*
 - d. Writing the publication**
- 2. Critically reviewing the publication for important intellectual content*
- 3. Final approval of the version to be published*
- 4. Agreement to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved.*

All those who meet these four criteria must be identified as authors. Partners who meet 1-3 of the criteria must be acknowledged (see section 8.5), but not identified as authors. In addition to being accountable for the parts of the work done, an author should be able to identify which co-authors are responsible for specific other parts of the work. The [CRedit framework](#) should be used as a default to adhere to the latest standards for acknowledging an author's specific contributions, although publishers may require the use of alternative frameworks. Authors should have confidence in the integrity of the contributions of their co-authors. All partners who meet the first criterion should have the opportunity to participate in the review, drafting, and final approval of the manuscript (i.e., the opportunity to meet criteria 2 and 3) to avoid disqualifying partners from authorship by preventing them from meeting all criteria. Therefore, the co-authors of a deliverable from which a scientific publication is derived must be invited to contribute to the derived

publication; however, they can only be identified as co-authors of the derived scientific publication if they meet the four threshold criteria described above.

The partners who conduct the work are responsible for identifying who meets these criteria and should do so when planning the work and as the work progresses. It is the collective responsibility of the authors to determine that all people named as authors meet all four criteria; journal editors are not responsible for determining authorship or arbitrating authorship conflicts. If agreement cannot be reached about who qualifies for authorship, the institution(s) where the work was performed should be asked to investigate.

8.2 Order of Authors

The criteria used to determine the order in which authors are listed on the byline may vary but are usually based on the contributions of each author. The order should be decided collectively by the author group and not by editors. If authors request removal or addition of an author after manuscript submission or publication, the listed authors and the author to be removed or added should provide the journal editors with an explanation and signed statement of agreement for the requested change.

8.3 Corresponding Author

The corresponding author is the partner who takes primary responsibility for communication with the journal during the manuscript submission, peer-review, and publication process. The corresponding author typically ensures that all the journal's administrative requirements, such as providing details of authorship, ethics committee approval, and disclosures of relationships and activities are properly completed and reported, although these duties may be delegated to one or more co-authors. The corresponding author should be available throughout the submission and peer-review process to respond to editorial queries in a timely way. They should also be available after publication to respond to critiques of the work and cooperate with any requests from the journal for data or additional information should questions about the paper arise after publication.

8.4 Acknowledgement of Equal Contribution of Authors

If multiple authors have contributed equally to the work this should be decided by the author group and not by editors, and this can be mentioned during submission. Equally, if the work has more than one senior (usually last) author this should be decided by the author group, and this can be mentioned during submission. Examples of acknowledgement of shared responsibility of the work can be: "These authors contributed equally to this work and share first authorship", "These authors contributed equally to this work and share senior authorship".

8.5 Acknowledgement of Non-Author Contributors

Contributors who meet 1-3 of the threshold criteria for authorship (see section 8.1) should be acknowledged but not listed as authors. Examples of activities that alone (without other contributions) require acknowledgement but do not qualify a contributor for authorship are acquisition of funding; general supervision of a research group or general administrative support; and writing assistance, technical editing, language editing, and proofreading. Those whose contributions do not justify authorship may be acknowledged individually or together as a group under a single heading (e.g., “Participating Investigators”). Their contribution should be specified (e.g., “served as scientific advisors”, “reviewed the study proposal”, “collected data”, “participated in writing or technical editing of the manuscript”, “provided access to research infrastructure”). In non-deliverable publications, BLUE4ALL must be acknowledged as the project as part of which the research was carried out using the following phrase:

This study was funded by the EU HORIZON project Blueprint demonstration for co-created effective, efficient and resilient networks of MPAs (BLUE4ALL, Project ID 101094014).

Because acknowledgment may imply endorsement by acknowledged individuals of a study’s data and conclusions, it is recommended that the corresponding author obtain written permission to be acknowledged from all acknowledged individuals.

9. References

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10. Annexes

10.1 Updated Informed Consent Form

PROJECT TITLE	BLUE4ALL
START DATE OF THE PROJECT	01-01-2023
END DATE OF THE PROJECT	31-12-2026
PROJECT WEBSITE	www.blue4all.eu

You have been invited to participate in research under the BLUE4ALL project in the form of a survey, workshop or an interview. Before participation, please read the information below carefully. If statements in the document are unclear to you, do not hesitate to ask the contact researcher for clarification.

1. Project summary

BLUE4ALL will align top-down regulatory demands about European (networks of) MPAs with bottom-up societal expectations to achieve effective, efficient and resilient MPAs and networks of MPAs which meet EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 objectives. By mobilizing stakeholders from BLUE4ALL's 25 Information Sites and Living Labs, i.e., locations across the Mediterranean Sea, the Baltic Sea and the North-East Atlantic regions where (networks of) MPAs have been established and from which lessons learned can be drawn about success and failure relative to how challenges were tackled, we will co-create robust and replicable social, governance, ecological and environmental tools to meet conservation and/or restoration objectives in socially sustainable and acceptable ways. These science-based tools will be tested in Living Labs, i.e., locations where (networks of) MPAs are in the process of establishment and where these tools can be fed into the ongoing MPA process. The operationalized and tested frameworks will ultimately be generalized into a Blueprint Platform for the co-creation of effective, efficient and resilient (networks of) MPAs. This scheme will separate generically encountered challenges and applied solutions from MPA (network) specific challenges and solutions and develop guidance in a user-friendly manner to end-users (i.e., MPA (network) managers and authorities). This guidance will take the shape of an interactive web-based Blueprint Platform directing the end-users to those challenges and solutions most applicable to their site(s). User-friendliness and applicability will be maximized by cross-checking the Blueprint Platform development with the actors and stakeholders of the Living Labs throughout the whole process of its development. Knowledge transfer and interaction with stakeholders and society-at-large at local to regional scales will lead to the development of a platform for MPA networking to interact with communities of practice and boost the BLUE4ALL legacy to restore our oceans and waters.

2. Purpose of data collection

You have been invited to participate in an interview, survey or workshop. Resulting data will be specifically used to

3. Benefit of participation

Participation is on an entirely voluntary basis and you may not directly benefit. However, you will make a substantial contribution to the BLUE4ALL project aims.

4. Risks of participation

There are no risks foreseen in participation

5. Compliance with ethical and legal regulations

We comply with EU and national ethical and legal regulations, including the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation 2016/680) framework of the EU.

6. Privacy and data protection

Data resulted from surveys and interviews will be recorded and stored on secure servers. This data will not include any personal identification, so that data cannot be traced back to you as the source of the data. Data might be processed and analysed for publication in reports, scientific journals and other forms of project outputs, only in anonymized form. None of the data will be transferred to third parties. Data collected in non-EU countries may be exported to BLUE4ALL partners in the EU. Retention time of the original research data is the same as the project duration, although the anonymized resultant data may be stored for longer periods of time to be used in future research.

7. Withdrawal of participation

At any point you may withdraw from participation by stopping the interview, survey or workshop.

8. Researcher contact

In case of any issues or questions you can contact:

Name: and contact:

9. Consent statement

By signing this form, I state that I have read all information on this document of informed consent, I understand the information provided, and I agree with the terms and conditions provided on the informed consent document.

.....
Research Participant	Signature	Date
.....

Researcher

Signature

Date

